

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND RESILIENCE AS PREDICTORS OF QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AMONG EDUCATORS: A CONVERGENT DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

This study employed mixed methods research, specifically convergent design, to determine the predicting effect of organizational culture and resilience on the quality work of life. The data were gathered from private higher education educators in Region XI, Philippines. Sets of validated adapted survey tools with a five-point Likert scale and interview guide were used to gather data. The statistical tools used to treat the quantitative data were mean and multiple regression analysis, while in the qualitative phase, thematic analysis was employed. In the quantitative phase, results showed that the level of organizational culture and resilience of educators were rated high and very high, while their level of quality of work life was rated high. Further, organizational culture and resilience significantly predict the quality of work life. In terms of lived experiences of participants, as regards the quality of work of life, six themes had emerged, which included respect in the learning environment, the balance between happiness and productivity, utmost support from the institution, just compensation, and a good working environment, engagement and recognition, and learning from a colleague. In terms of beliefs, attitudes, and commitment as shaped by their experiences, six themes emerged: self-realization, progress through flexibility, self-growth, positive mindset, personal adjustment to circumstances, and professionalism. Finally, the nature of data integration revealed merging – converging.

Keywords: *Education, leadership organizational culture, resilience, quality work of life, convergent, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers' quality of work life has been significantly disrupted due to the changes in learning modality. As a result, many teachers struggle to balance workload and family concerns during the health crisis (Lizana, 2021). Moreover, it is apparent that if these teachers cannot deal with these challenges, it may harm school organizations. Thus, ineffective teachers can be costly to organizations and often lead to poor work-life balance (Sheppard, 2016).

In the United States, approximately half of the teachers leave their jobs due to toxic organizational culture, which may negatively impact their well-being (Nathaniel et al., 2018). In addition, Rasheed et al. (2016) discovered that among 30,000 employees of educational institutions worldwide, between 28 and 56 percent of these teachers experience psychological burnout, which most likely affects their quality of life at work (Dhamija et al., 2019). In addition, Ozamiz-Etxebarria et al. (2021) also discovered a decrease in teachers' quality of life in Northern Spain. As a result, 50.6 percent of teachers reported being under stress, 49.5 percent reported suffering from anxiety, and 32.2 percent reported experiencing depression.

Further, according to a report released in 2012 during the National Dialogue Education, teachers worldwide consistently demonstrate a reduced ability to provide a strong commitment to work. The report also revealed that one of the challenges that schools face today is maintaining teacher efficiency, which could be attributed to school leaders' abilities to establish a healthy organizational culture (Veysel, 2014). Furthermore, a worker with low commitment to work may develop a negative attitude toward his or her work, manifesting as behavioral indicators such as absenteeism and intent to leave the organization (Rehman et al., 2021).

In a study conducted in China, the psychological dimension of teachers' quality of work life has been low; older teachers have shown the highest levels of psychological distress (Li et al., 2020). More specifically, 13.67 percent of the 88,611 teachers polled reported workplace anxiety. In addition, a study conducted in Croatia with a sample of teachers by Maslach et al. (2016) found that psychological burnout significantly impacted their quality of work life.

In the Philippines, the closure of schools and social isolation implemented globally has decreased teachers' quality of work life (Talidong & Toquero, 2020). Teachers are transitioning through an uncertain period in their professional and personal lives (Allen et al., 2020). Another study by Rabacal et al. (2020) found that the quality of teachers' work life was moderate and had the highest impact on their personal safety and mental health. Previous studies have found a negative association between organizational culture and quality of work life (Pereira et al., 2021). Thus, their investigations demonstrated that increased burnout would likely reduce an individual's quality of work life.

Additionally, the negative impact of burnout on the quality of life can affect motivation and professional achievement among employees (Moraes et al., 2019). Also, a large body of evidence shows resilience contributes to a better quality of work life (Windle et al., 2011; Sutton-Grier et al., 2011). Moreover, Pendse and Ruikar (2013) contend that workers who have demonstrated greater resilience also tend to have higher life satisfaction and quality of work life.

The organizational culture within educational institutions plays a significant role in shaping the quality of work life experienced by educators. Organizational culture refers to the shared values, beliefs, and norms that guide the behavior and interactions of individuals within an organization (Schein, 2010). It encompasses leadership style, communication patterns, decision-making processes, and work environment. Hartnell et al. (2011) conducted a meta-analysis investigating the relationship between organizational culture and effectiveness. They found that a positive organizational culture, characterized by a supportive and empowering work environment, enhances job satisfaction and employee well-being. Such a culture encourages collaboration, professional development, and work-life balance, which are crucial factors for improving the quality of the work life of educators.

Moreover, Trivellas and Reklitis (2014) examined the relationship between organizational culture and employee satisfaction in a Greek organization. They found that a positive and supportive organizational culture positively influenced employee satisfaction, which, in turn, contributed to the overall quality of work life. The finding highlights the importance of fostering a culture that values and supports educators' well-being and professional growth.

Furthermore, a study by Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2017) investigated the relationship between teacher resilience and well-being, job satisfaction, and motivation. They found that resilient educators experienced higher levels of job satisfaction and motivation and lower levels of emotional exhaustion. The finding suggests that resilience contributes positively to the quality of work life by enhancing well-being and intrinsic motivation.

Moreover, a study by Jansen et al. (2016) focused specifically on the relationship between resilience and work-related well-being of beginning teachers. They found that resilient beginning teachers experienced less emotional exhaustion and reported higher levels of work-related well-being. The finding highlights the importance of resilience, particularly in the early stages of a teaching career, for promoting a positive work experience. A study by Day et al. (2016) also explored the relationship between teacher resilience and job satisfaction across different educational systems. They found that higher levels of resilience were associated with greater job satisfaction among educators in various cultural and educational contexts.

Several studies have been conducted on the bivariate relationship between organizational culture and quality of work life (Narehan et al., 2014), as well as resilience and quality of life (Ristevska-Dimitrovska et al., 2015). However, more needs to be done to combine organizational culture and resilience as predictors in the relationship model that predicts quality of work life. Although some studies describe the mediating nature of resilience (Sarrionandia et al., 2018; Yu & Chae, 2020), these studies utilized only other predictors of quality of work life, such as mental well-being and family functioning. Thus, it is rarely found in the literature that looks at the roles of organizational culture and resilience in this context, and more research is needed to determine how organizational culture and resilience predict the quality of work life.

Also, most studies conducted on the quality of work life focused on healthcare-related subjects such as nurses, medical professionals, and patients (Woon et al., 2021); less has been done among teachers. In addition, these studies utilized quantitative designs to predict the quality of work life; thus, the researcher has not come across a study that utilizes a mixed-methods research design.

The study shall provide important information that school leaders can use to develop programs that will improve the quality of life of teachers. Moreover, the study results can be used by teachers to have a personal intervention on particular dimensions that can be addressed at their level. The conclusion of this research could help the teachers identify areas of strength and areas that need to be developed to function more effectively as facilitators of learning and primary implementers of the curriculum. School stakeholders may also benefit from the impact of this research on the leadership and instructional management of Deans and Program Heads by utilizing the study results as a basis for crafting, improving, and sustaining leadership and instructional management-related programs and initiatives. Further, the result of this study provides an essential foundation for ongoing research and dialogue regarding the commitment of teachers in educational institutions as an organization. It could also provide future researchers with valuable knowledge.

Finally, using a convergent parallel mixed methods design, this study sought to determine the impact of organizational culture and resilience on the quality of work life of teachers in a private higher education institution in the Davao Region. Thus, the results of this study could provide empirical evidence of the interconnectedness of the variables, as mentioned earlier in the locality. Moreover, by examining those variables, issues on teachers' quality of work life within the scope of the study could be resolved with greater probability.

Lastly, the generated data would be used to create information that would be shared with the private tertiary colleges participating in the study and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED). Additionally, the findings may be presented to various research fora and published in education journals with a leadership and management focus. In order to improve the leadership and management of school leaders, which may be related to the success of making schools effective, the results and discussions provide the substantive explanation to be used for their improvement plan.

Research Questions

This study determined the influence of organizational culture and resilience on the quality of work life of educators in Higher Education Institutions in Region XI. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the status of organizational culture, resilience, and quality of work life of educators as perceived by the participants?
2. Do the combined and singular influence of organizational culture and resilience on quality of work life of educator significant?
3. What are the lived experiences of the participants concerning quality of work life?
4. How do the experiences relative to organizational culture and resilience shape the beliefs, attitudes, and commitments of the participants to exhibit quality of work life?
5. To what extent do the qualitative data corroborate with the quantitative data?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, specifically the convergent design. Further, the quantitative phase employed the descriptive–correlational design. In this study, the quality of the work life of educators was determined through the influence of organizational culture and resilience. For the qualitative phase, the phenomenological approach was utilized in this study.

This study was conducted in Region XI, particularly with the Higher Education Institutions, Region XI, composed of eighty-two HEIs. Specifically, sixty-two HEIs were from Davao del Sur, eleven were from Davao del Norte, six were from Davao de Oro, and three were from Davao Oriental.

For the quantitative phase, 331 educators from private HEIs in Region XI were the study's respondents. They were selected using purposive sampling. The inclusion criteria include full-time teachers for at least three years. Any respondent who did not meet such criteria was automatically excluded from this study. For the qualitative phase, 17 educators from the HEIs in Region XI were invited to participate in the IDI and FGD. Ten participants were invited for IDI and seven for the FGD. These participants were selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. However, it is essential to note that these participants were distinct from the 331 respondents in the quantitative strand of the study. The results of the IDI and FGD were utilized to explore the emerging themes based on their experiences.

For the quantitative phase, the study used three adapted questionnaires that pertain to organizational culture, resilience, and quality of work life. It was designed to obtain necessary information from the respondents. Such an instrument used the five–point Likert Scale with five as the highest and one as the lowest. Before the study, the sets of questionnaires were subjected to content and construct-related validity. Five expert validators have done the process; three of them were from the panel members, and the remaining two were from the external. Revisions to the questionnaire were done following the suggestions of the expert validators.

For organizational culture, the questionnaire was adapted from Tang et al. (2000), which assessed the status of organizational culture manifested by educators in the academic institution. A reliability coefficient of .988 suggests that the pilot test yielded highly reliable and consistent participant responses. This indicates that the modified statement will likely effectively capture the intended construct or measure the targeted variable accurately. This is a five-point Likert questionnaire that consists of four parameters: family oriented/loyalty, open communication, team approach, and manager knowledge, and each parameter has five, seven, nine, and nine items, respectively.

The instrument used in measuring the educators' Resilience is a tool adapted from Platsidou et al. (2021), which was used to assess the status of Resilience experienced by educators in the academe. After some modification, this has gone through a pilot test which has a reliability coefficient of .91. This implies that a reliability coefficient of .91 indicates that the pilot test produced dependable and consistent responses from participants, suggesting that the modified statement is likely to accurately measure the intended construct or variable with a satisfactory level of reliability. This five-point Likert questionnaire consists of three parameters: motivational and professional Resilience,

Social Resilience, and Emotional Resilience. Each parameter has eight, six, and five items, respectively.

In assessing the Quality of Work Life status, the questionnaire was adapted from Swamy et al. (2015). The pilot test results were highly reliable and consistent, as indicated by the reliability coefficient of .98. This suggests that the altered statement is highly likely to capture the desired construct or measure the desired variable accurately. This is a five-point Lickert checklist which is composed of nine parameters, namely: work environment, organizational culture and climate, relation and cooperation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction, and job security, autonomy of work and adequacy of resources. Also, this tool was scored and quantified using the scale in the next page. The three instruments that were used in the quantitative phase were adapted questionnaires. The modified questionnaires had a reliability value ranging from .91 to .98, which indicated that the instrument was reliable for measuring the independent and dependent variables.

However, to determine the cross-cultural validity and reliability of the questionnaires, they were subjected to content validity by experts who evaluated the clarity of directions and items, presentations of times, and the suitability of items, and adequateness of items per category, attainment of the purpose, objectivity, scale, and evaluation in the rating system.

In the qualitative phase, the researcher utilized a self-made interview guide consisting of structured questions during the conduct of IDI and FGD. A panel of experts validated the guide questions. Revisions were made based on the experts' comments, corrections, and suggestions. The interview guide was used to gather data from the participants who answered the probing questions.

Data Gathering Procedure

The collection of both the quantitative and qualitative data was conducted at the same time. The researcher undertook specific procedures in conducting the study and sought the approval of the Dean of the Graduate School to conduct the study through a letter request. Upon approval, the Ethical Clearance was secured from the University of the Immaculate Conception - Research Ethics Committee (UIC -REC) to ensure the ethical soundness of the paper. After this, the permission letter from the Dean was formally forwarded to each School President of the private HEIs in Region XI for permission and endorsement to conduct the study. After this, the researcher coordinated with the school heads for the data gathering and interview schedule.

In the conduct of the quantitative phase of the study, the researcher sought consent from the respondents, and they were informed on the entire process of the study, the purpose of the study, the different dimensions of ethical consideration during data gathering, and that their participation in the study was voluntary. Before administering the survey questionnaire, the respondents were requested to sign the Informed Consent Form (ICF). They were asked to return the ICF to the researcher as evidence of their voluntary participation in the study. Only those who signed the ICF were considered as the respondents to the study. The three survey questionnaires were administered to the participants on the same day to avoid mood changes. The said form was sent back to the researcher as soon as the respondents finished accomplishing all the questionnaires for organizational culture, resilience, and quality of work life. The quantitative data was then consolidated, tallied, and treated with statistical tools by the respondents.

In the qualitative strand of the study, the researcher conducted IDI and FGD to strengthen the investigation further. Like in the quantitative strand, the researcher strictly observed the appropriate protocols in working in the qualitative strand.

The individual in–depth interviews were conducted after the participants signed the ICF and confirmed their availability. The validated guide questions, focusing on the three variables of the study, were used during the interviews. Also, the participants were informed of the recordings to ensure the validity and reliability of the responses.

Additionally, the FGD were employed to obtain a detailed and broader range of information from a few informants to discuss the topic of interest, in this case, matters on their quality of work life. The participants were requested to sign the ICF to confirm their involvement in the study. In the conduct of the FGD, the researcher acted as the facilitator to stimulate the discussion through an interview guide. Also, the selected participants were oriented before the conduct of the FGD to ensure that their ethical rights were not violated. Also, the participants were informed that the FGD would be recorded. Data gathered from participants through the IDI and FGD were sorted and analyzed.

Data Analysis

This research used appropriate statistical treatment to classify, analyze, and interpret results. Since the study utilized the mixed methods approach, quantitative and qualitative strategies were employed to extract the desired data. For the quantitative strand, mean and multiple regression were employed while for the qualitative strand, a step–by–step process was used to analyze the verbatim data gathered by the researcher through IDI and FGD. Collaizi's Method (1978), composed of seven steps, was observed to uncover the participants' genuine experience regarding the phenomenon being studied.

RESULTS

Table 1
Level of Organizational Culture

Indicators/ Items	Mean	SD	Description
A. Family Orientation/Loyalty: Our school is...			
1 trying to create a unique family atmosphere	4.19	.82	High
2 emphasizing strong loyalty and dedication	4.21	.82	Very High
3 treating each employee as a total person	4.18	.86	High
4 having a real interest in the welfare and overall satisfaction of those who work in school.	4.08	.87	High
5 being open to questions	4.05	.92	High
Category Mean	4.14	.76	High
B. Open Communication: Our school is...			
1 valuing our ideas and inputs	4.10	.84	High
2 giving us the freedom to express ideas	4.09	.86	High
3 emphasizing open communication	4.09	.91	High
4 encouraging people to speak up when they disagree	4.00	.93	High

Category Mean		4.07	.82	High
C. Team Approach: Our school is...				
1	giving us a chance to meet with our direct supervisor one-to-one at least twice a year to discuss performance and goals	4.12	.88	High
2	encouraging people in our group to work as a team	4.21	.86	Very High
3	encouraging people who work in our group to exchange opinions and ideas	4.21	.84	Very High
Category Mean		4.18	.78	High
D. Manager Knowledge: Our school head is...				
1	often communicating the overall organizational goals to us	4.05	.90	High
2	having the knowledge and training to be a good leader	4.16	.92	High
3	providing help, training, and guidance so that we can improve our performance.	4.12	.95	High
Category Mean		4.11	.83	High
Overall Mean		4.13	.72	High

Table 2
Level of Resilience of Educators

Indicators/ Items		Mean	SD	Description
A. Motivation and Professional Resilience: I am...				
1	setting goals and work towards achieving them	4.43	.62	Very High
2	being persistent in my work	4.41	.66	Very High
3	putting effort to do my job well because it is important to me	4.60	.56	Very High
4	liking challenges in my work	4.28	.65	Very High
5	having realistic expectations of myself as a teacher	4.39	.65	Very High
6	enjoying learning when I am at work	4.50	.62	Very High
7	reflecting on my teaching and learning to make future plans	4.48	.62	Very High
8	being well organized in my school work	4.25	.70	Very High
Category Mean		4.42	.50	Very High
B. Social Resilience: I am...				
1	looking at a situation in a number of ways to find a solution in my work	4.37	.60	Very High
2	being good communicator in my role as a teacher	4.27	.66	Very High
3	generally resolving conflicts with others when I am at work	4.14	.72	High

4	being good at building relationships in new school environments	4.26	.73	Very High
5	seeking help from colleagues when I am unsure of something	4.39	.69	Very High
6	viewing situations from other people's perspectives at work	4.23	.67	Very High
Category Mean		4.28	.53	Very High
C. Emotional Resilience: I am...				
1	generally being optimistic at school	4.27	.70	Very High
2	balancing my role as a teacher with other dimensions in my life	4.30	.67	Very High
3	managing to stay calm when I feel upset or angry at school	4.27	.72	Very High
4	usually finding the funny side of challenging school situations after reflection	4.25	.63	Very High
5	not taking it personally when something goes wrong at school	4.12	.72	High
Category Mean		4.24	.53	Very High
Overall Mean		4.31	.46	Very High

Table 3
Level of Quality of Work Life

Indicators/ Items		Mean	SD	Description
A. Work Environment: Our school is...				
1	having a school work environment that is good and highly motivating	4.07	.82	High
2	having a working condition that is good	4.06	.81	High
3	having it is easy to take time off during our work to take care of personal or family matters	4.14	.82	High
4	offering sufficient opportunities to develop our own abilities	4.05	.86	High
5	providing enough information to discharge our responsibilities	3.97	.83	High
6	giving a lot of work empowerment to decide about our own style and peace at work	4.02	.83	High
Category Mean		4.05	.69	High
B. Organization Culture and Climate: Our school is...				
1	having cooperation among all the departments for achieving the goals	4.07	1.32	High
2	giving us freedom to offer comments and suggestions on our performance	4.04	.84	High
3	making us proud to be working for it	4.27	.80	Very High
4	involving us in making decisions that affect our work	4.02	.87	High
5	welcoming us on our job regardless of our gender	4.44	.68	Very High

G. Job Satisfaction and Job Security:

Our school is...

1	making us feel comfortable and satisfied with our job	4.13	.79	High
2	making us feel quite secure about our job	3.93	.94	High
3	allowing us to be as productive as we could be whatever conditions on our job	4.09	.80	High
4	establishing an organization that protect employees' interest	3.96	.91	High
5	making us feel that our job is stable	3.83	.96	High
6	making us feel that our earnings are fair when compared to the others doing the same type of work in other companies	3.78	.98	High
7	following a good procedure for job rotation	3.86	.89	High
8	making us feel that our work allow us to do my best in a particular area	4.16	1.88	High

Category Mean	3.97	.76	High
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H. Autonomy of Work: Our school is...

1	letting us use our skills and abilities in our job	4.35	.63	Very High
2	allowing a flexi-time option	3.98	.91	High
3	allowing part of our job to be done at home	4.00	.92	High
4	making us find my job stress free	3.56	1.05	High
5	making us ready to take on additional responsibilities with my job	3.63	1.05	High
6	having a balance between stated objectives and resources provided	3.78	.88	High

Category of Mean	3.88	.68	High
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I. Adequacy of Resources: Our school is...

1	having many defined channels for information exchange and transfer	3.87	.73	High
2	providing resources to facilitate our performance	3.97	.82	High
3	Having satisfactory communication and information flow between the departments	3.87	.87	High

Category Mean	3.90	.72	High
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Overall Mean	3.98	.62	High
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Table 4
Significance of the Influence of Organizational Culture and Resilience on Quality of Work Life

	Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	p-value	Interpretation
Organizational Culture	.697	21.383	.000	Significant
Resilience	.263	8.064	.000	Significant

R = .867
R Square = .751
F = 495.778
p value = .000

Table 5.1
Profile of the Participants

Participant No.	Codes of the Participants	Sex	Data Source Group	Divisions
01	IDIP1	M	IDI	Davao City
02	IDIP2	F	IDI	Davao City
03	IDIP3	M	IDI	Davao City
04	IDIP4	M	IDI	Davao City
05	IDIP5	F	IDI	Davao del Sur
06	IDIP6	M	IDI	Davao City
07	IDIP7	M	IDI	Davao del Sur
08	IDIP8	F	IDI	Davao City
09	IDIP9	F	IDI	Davao City
10	IDIP10	F	IDI	Davao City
11	FGDP1	M	FGD	Davao City
12	FGDP2	M	FGD	Davao City
13	FGDP3	F	FGD	Davao City
14	FGDP4	F	FGD	Davao City
15	FGDP5	F	FGD	Davao City
16	FGDP6	F	FGD	Davao City
17	FGDP7	F	FGD	Davao City

Table 5.2
Lived experiences of Participants concerning Quality of Work Life

Themes	Core Ideas
Respect in learning environment	Having an efficient atmosphere with colleague and superior
	Having flexible time for duty explains the quality of work life
	Having open communication holds reason for a quality of work life
	Earning the right respect from colleague and superior
	Receiving equal treatment from colleagues
Balance between happiness and productivity	Having a happy environment
	Being productive employee of the institution
	Being able to attend to school duty while fulfilling family responsibilities
Just compensation and good working environment	Having a fulfilling quality of work life by being able to deliver what is required in the institution
	Having satisfying quality of work life due to the just compensation being received
	Having a satisfactory quality of work life due the smooth working environment
Utmost support from the institution	The culture of the school solidifies the quality of work life
	Providence of importance to employees makes up a quality of work life
	The quality advocated by the school keeps the motivation up and running that defines quality of work life
	Having a supportive administrator for better quality of work life
Engagement and recognition	Having been afforded of every opportunity is equated to a quality of work life
	Having recognition due to student performance life licensure examination is what make a quality of work life
	Having been exposed to several training and seminar constitute quality of work life
Learning from colleague	Constant learning from the top management contributes to a quality of work life
	Motivation coming from superior add up to a quality of work life
	Learning from seasoned instructors constitute quality of work life

Table 6.1
Roles of Experiences in Shaping the Belief of the
Participants in Quality of Work Life

Themes	Core Ideas
Self-realization	Learning to be more committed to teaching
	Realizing that good quality learning environment is necessary in teaching and learning process
	Strengthening one's personality by being tapped of one's expertise
	The presence of the opportunity to grow breaks down one's limitation
Progress through flexibility	Becoming progressive in one's work by being more resilient
	Being open to possibilities all the time
	Learning to be flexible and not getting fixated to previous learning

Table 6.2
Roles of Experiences in Shaping the Attitude
of the Participants in Quality of Work Life

Self-growth	Pushing oneself to use potentials related to teaching
	Trusting oneself of one's potential
	Never remaining less of oneself in the process of learning experience
Positive mindset	Learning to love and accept every time
	Becoming ready all the time and learn to anticipate things
	Taking things positively amidst criticism
	Learning to easily accept the unexpected happenings

Table 6.3
Roles of Experiences in Shaping the Commitments of the Participants in Quality
of Work Life

Personal adjustment to circumstances	Living with the change for the better throughout the course of teaching and learning process
	Embracing changes happening in the workplace
	Becoming well-oriented of one's responsibilities
	Learning to be compassionate to all occasion that would come along the way

Professionalism	Developing one's personality into becoming more professional
	Growing professionally in the course of the entire experience

Table 7
Joint Display of the Salient Qualitative and Quantitative Findings

Aspect or Focal Point	Quantitative Findings	Qualitative Findings	Nature of Integration
Organizational Culture	<p>Table 1 on Organizational Culture of teachers under indicator, Family Orientation/Loyalty, on item, emphasizing strong loyalty and dedication, is rated Very High, M=4.21, SD=.82</p> <p>Table 1 on Organizational Culture of teachers under indicator, Open Communication, on item, giving me the freedom to express ideas, is rated High, M=4.00, SD=.864</p> <p>Table 1 on Organizational Culture of teachers under indicator, Team Approach, on item, encouraging people who work in my group to exchange opinions and ideas, is rated High, M=4.00, SD=.840</p> <p>Table 1 on Organizational Culture of teachers under indicator, Manager Knowledge, on item, having the knowledge and training to be a good</p>	<p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has core ideas on the aspect of respecting the learning environment, and providing a balance between work and family.</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>respect in learning environment</i> include code which illustrates that open communication promotes employee happiness at work, engagement and productivity. Furthermore, open communication bridges cultural division, promotes inclusion, and clarifies expectations</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>learning from colleague</i> contains core ideas highlighting learning and motivation from colleagues and superiors.</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>learning from colleague</i> which contain core ideas such as constant learning from the top management, motivation from superiors, and continued support from administrators</p>	Merging-Converging

	leader, is rated High, M=4.16, SD=.916	add to their quality of work life.	
Resilience			
	<p>Table 2 on Resilience of teachers under indicator, Motivational and Professional Resilience, on item, putting effort to do my job well because it is important to me, is rated Very High, M=4.60, SD=. 555</p> <p>Table 2 on Resilience of teachers under indicator, Social Resilience, on item, seeking help from colleagues when I am unsure of something, is rated Very High, M=4.39, SD= .694</p> <p>Table 2 on Resilience of teachers under indicator, Emotional Resilience, on item, balancing my role as a teacher with other dimensions in my life, is rated Very High, M=4.30, SD= .669</p>	<p>Table 6 on lived experiences, has a theme self-growth which contain code such as pushing oneself to use potentials related to teaching, and never remaining less of oneself in the process of learning experience</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences involves core ideas that include learning from seasoned instructors constitute quality of work life under the theme <i>learning from colleague</i>.</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme balance between being happy and being productive with core ideas such as having a balanced quality work of life by being able to attend to school duty and family responsibilities</p>	Merging-Converging
Quality of Work Life			
	<p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Work Environment, on item, having it is easy to take time off during our work to take care of personal or family matters, is rated High, M=4.14, SD= .816</p> <p>The very high rating for <i>I am welcome on my job regardless of my gender</i> (M=4.44), and high rating for the item <i>The wage policies adopted by my school are good</i> (M=3.95)</p>	<p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme balance between being happy and being productive with core ideas that include having a balanced quality work of life by being able to attend to school duty and family responsibilities.</p> <p>Table 5.2 on the lived experiences involves earning the right respect from colleagues and having equal treatment received from colleagues, and having a satisfying quality of work life due to just compensation being received.</p>	Merging-Converging

	<p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Relation and Co-operation, on item, having me get good support from my subordinates, is rated High, M=4.17 SD= .734</p> <p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Training and development, on item, helping employees achieve the required skill for performing the job effectively through training programs, is rated High, M=4.05 SD= .878</p> <p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Compensation and Rewards, on item, paying a salary by considering responsibilities at work, is rated High, M=3.93 SD= .901</p> <p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Facilities , on item, providing the social security benefits like Philhealth/ Medical Reimbursements and so on , is rated Very High, M=4.35 SD= 767</p> <p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers</p>	<p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, has a theme <i>learning from colleague</i> contains core ideas highlighting learning and motivation from colleagues and superiors, and the theme respect in learning environment with a component of earning the right respect from colleague and superior</p> <p>Table 6 has a theme on Professionalism which consist of a core idea that states growing professionally in the course of the entire experience, and Table 5.2 theme that involves engagement and recognition highlights exposures to several training and seminar constitute quality of work life</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, represents the theme that constitute just compensation and good working environment</p> <p>Table 5.2 on lived experiences, represents the theme that constitute just compensation and good working environment, specifically with the core idea having satisfying quality of work life due to the just compensation being received</p> <p>Table 6 on the theme about self-realization, has a core idea that speaks on realization that good quality learning environment is necessary in teaching and learning process</p>	
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	<p>under indicator, Job Satisfaction and Job security, on item, making me feel that my work allows me to do my best in a particular area, is rated High, M=4.16 SD= 1.879</p> <p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Autonomy of Work, on item, letting me use my skills and abilities in my job, is rated High, M=4.35 SD= .630</p> <p>Table 3 on Quality of Work Life of teachers under indicator, Adequacy of Resources, on item, providing resources to facilitate my performance, is rated High, M=3.97 SD= .822</p>	<p>Table 6 on the aspect of self-growth which highlight the core idea about pushing oneself to use potentials related to teaching</p> <p>Table 75.2 on lived experiences, represents the theme utmost support from the institution especially on the providence given to employees which makes up quality of work life</p>	
Influence of organizational culture and resilience on quality of work life	The standardized coefficients and p-values indicate that both organizational culture and resilience are significant predictors of quality of work life (p<.05)	Positive organizational culture and resilience can contribute to a better quality of work life, which is characterized by respect, balance, just compensation, support, engagement, and learning	Merging-Converging

DISCUSSION

Level of Organizational Culture

As assessed by the participants, the level of organizational culture is high. This implies that organizational culture is oftentimes manifested among educators in Region XI. This denotes that the educators in Region XI experienced good organizational culture. This indicates that educators in the region frequently encounter positive and supportive manifestations of organizational culture. Good organizational culture contributes to a supportive and conducive work environment for educators, promoting their overall well-being and job satisfaction. This finding conforms to the study by Gómez et al. (2019), in which the results indicated that a positive and supportive culture, where employees feel

valued, empowered, and have opportunities for growth and development, contributed to higher levels of employee engagement.

Moreover, the results support the conclusion of Dahlvig (2018) regarding elements that contribute to a positive work environment that fosters productivity, engagement, and professional growth among educators. Lastly, Rofifah et al. (2021) emphasized that a strong organizational culture can have several benefits for educators, and it can enhance their job satisfaction, motivation, and commitment to their work, leading to improved performance and quality of teaching.

Family Orientation/Loyalty. The results of this study revealed that the level of family orientation of educators is high. This implies that family orientation is oftentimes manifested. This means that the educators have shared a purpose and common set core in establishing a strong institutional tie between educators. The high level of family orientation among educators indicates that they are also engaged in a continuous process of developing that they also share the same common mission of providing effective and quality education to students.

This result aligns with the study of Durrah (2022), which found that establishing a family-oriented organizational culture in educational institutions contributes to a positive work environment and improved student outcomes. Furthermore, family orientation provides educators assistance to a colleague by assisting them with their work, especially when the workload is heavy, and deadlines are tight, even if this means taking on additional tasks on top of required responsibilities (Darabi et al., 2016). Lastly, having a high level of family orientation in the educational context means that educators prioritize collaboration, mutual support, and a sense of belonging within their professional community. Kools et al. (2016) state that educators who exhibit a family orientation are more likely to work together toward a shared vision, establish strong relationships, and create a positive work environment that nurtures professional growth and development.

Open Communication. This study revealed that the level of open communication, as assessed by the participants, is high. This means that open communication is oftentimes manifested among educators in Region XI. This denotes that the schools value open communication among educators. This result coincides with Li et al.'s (2020) study, which indicated that open communication positively influenced employee knowledge-sharing behaviors and facilitated organizational learning processes. The study emphasized the importance of creating a supportive and inclusive communication climate to promote knowledge exchange and continuous learning within organizations.

Moreover, open communication facilitates knowledge exchange, fosters trust and understanding, and promotes teamwork among educators. It allows for effective problem-solving, collaboration on instructional strategies, and sharing of best practices (Lin et al., 2019). Finally, a study by Kiviniemi (2014) examined the impact of open communication on organizational commitment and employee well-being. The results revealed that open communication practices were positively related to organizational commitment and employee well-being.

Team Approach. The findings also revealed that the level of team approach among educators in Region XI is also high. This indicates that team approach is oftentimes manifested among educators. This means that educators use the team approach to improve their professional practice and raise their and others' productivity. This is parallel with the study of Reeves et al. (2017) that state educators collaborate to

make decisions to improve teamwork and achieve higher job performance and student outcomes. The school's educators' team functions as a result of efficient communication and cooperation between the various school stakeholders. The school also allows teachers to practice interpersonal skills by starting teamwork seminars. Collaborative learning sessions offer teachers a structured and supportive environment to engage with their peers, exchange ideas, and share their professional knowledge (Cecchin et al., 2021). Thus, these sessions provide valuable opportunities for teachers to practice and develop their interpersonal skills, such as active listening, effective communication, empathy, and collaboration (Brundiers et al., 2017). By engaging in these interactions, teachers enhance their professional growth while contributing to the collective knowledge and improvement of the teaching profession.

Manager Knowledge. This dimension of manager knowledge was also rated high. This means that manager knowledge is oftentimes manifested in the organization. This conforms to the study of Aminizadeh (2021), which states that high manager knowledge indicates a commitment to professional development and continuous learning within the organization. This suggests that the manager's knowledge is a valuable asset to any organization because it helps to increase productivity and eliminate inefficiencies. Ensuring school leaders can effectively manage their teachers in the workplace is especially important, making preserving a core culture harder to achieve. Thus, a knowledgeable school leader can help an organization eliminate ambiguity (Edmondson, 2012). Lastly, the knowledge of a modern organization's managers is critical to its success; in a modern environment, an excellent leader is a company's most important commodity, the most helpful asset of an institution, and a source of medium-term (Luthans et al., 2021). This, in turn, contributes to the overall effectiveness and success of the organization.

Level of Resilience of Educators

This study disclosed that the level of resilience among educators, as assessed by the participants, is very high. This implies that resilience is consistently demonstrated among educators in Region XI. This means educators can deal with natural stressors and difficulties in the classroom and can adapt to stressful situations at work. Furthermore, teaching is a constantly changing profession, and some of these changes are within the educator's control.

More importantly, educators demonstrate resilience in the workplace by demonstrating positive adaptation and coping mechanisms. These coping behaviors enable educators to achieve relatively good outcomes despite significant, ongoing stresses or adversities. This finding supports the claim of Howe et al. (2012) that educators can effectively handle stressful situations in the organization to achieve their organizational goals. The results conform to the study of Goleman (2021) that educators in the region possess strong adaptive capacities and can effectively cope with challenges and setbacks in their professional lives. The high level of resilience among educators indicates their ability to bounce back from adversity, maintain a positive mindset, and continue performing at a high level despite difficulties. Lastly, Shanafelt et al. (2017) stressed that resilience is a crucial characteristic for educators, given the demanding nature of their profession. Educators often face challenges such as heavy workloads, time constraints, student behavior issues, and external pressures. The ability to remain

resilient in these challenges is essential for maintaining well-being, job satisfaction, and overall effectiveness in the classroom.

Motivation and Professional Resilience. This dimension of resilience is rated very high. This implies that the educators' motivation and professional resilience are always evident in setting task goals and working to achieve them. This means that the educator emphasizes the importance of putting effort into their job well in the school. This finding corresponds with the findings of Beltman et al. (2011), who revealed that educators can thrive in stressful situations. Educators' choices in responding to challenging situations reflect their attitude and willingness to act, demonstrating resilience in the workplace. Thus, educators must be aware of their strengths in difficult situations while enjoying learning at work. This supports the study of Tricarico et al. (2015) that emphasized the role of effective awareness of strength in the difficult situation of educators. These include persistence at work so that teachers may do their best work and students can learn to their full potential. The high rating of this dimension of resilience suggests that educators in the study have a strong sense of self-motivation, dedication, and a growth mindset. It signifies their ability to maintain a positive attitude, adapt to changes, and remain resilient despite setbacks or difficulties. This level of motivation and professional resilience contributes to their overall effectiveness as educators and their ability to positively impact student learning outcomes (Durksen et al., 2017).

Social Resilience. This dimension of resilience is also rated as very high. This implies that the educators' resilience in society is always evident. This means that educators can look at ways to find solutions at work by building good relationships in new school environments and seeking help from their colleagues.

Having undergone workplace negativity, educators have learned to manage complex situations and broadened their perspectives to see the brighter side of things. They learn to be more adaptable, tolerant, and open to whatever consequences arise. They also learn to recognize that painful experiences can be used to improve themselves (Neff et al., 2015). Furthermore, because such events are likely to occur in an institution, it is prudent to cultivate the principle of creative cooperation. This principal values differences among members of an organization. The differences include the mental, emotional, and psychological states. This outcome is also supported by Beverly Irby's (2002) Synergistic Leadership Theory, which takes diversity into account. This theory offers a framework for further interactions and dynamic tensions between organizational culture, external forces, beliefs, attitudes, and values (Lunenburg, 2011).

Emotional Resilience. This dimension of resilience is also rated as very high. This implies that the teachers' resilience in their emotions is always evident. In leading in the aspect of emotions, the educators recognize and understand the balance of the role of a teacher with other life dimensions. Further, this finding supports the claim of McDaniel et al. (2016) that when educators struggle with their emotional well-being, it can affect many aspects of their lives. Because many of us spend most of our week at work, this is one area that suffers the most.

Moreover, it should be no surprise that their emotional resilience can significantly influence teachers' engagement and connection to their jobs. When someone struggles with their emotional well-being, the quality of their work and even their attendance can suffer (Gu et al., 2013). Finally, teachers' emotional resilience is vital to their overall job satisfaction, well-being, and retention in the teaching profession. By effectively managing

their emotions, teachers are better equipped to handle the emotional demands of their work and avoid burnout. They are more likely to experience job satisfaction, engagement, and a sense of fulfillment in their teaching roles (Chan et al., 2020).

Level of Quality of work Life

This study revealed that the quality of work life among educators, as assessed by the participants, is high. This implies that the educators in Region XI oftentimes observe the quality of work life. The findings further showed that educators experienced happiness in the working conditions of their schools. Happy teachers imply better work performance (Bullough, 2011). Furthermore, productivity is bound to rise when the quality of life at work is stable. As a result, teacher retention at work is high. This situation benefited employees, their families, and the organization. This study also supports the claim of Goldsmith (2011), who stated that happy people could function well in organizations and use appropriate resources and creative ideas to solve problems. Daily, they are confronted with engaging in every work situation that is appropriate for the given situation, so the quality of work life is essential. Lastly, high quality of work life can contribute to lower stress levels and burnout among educators. When educators have access to resources, support systems, and a positive work environment, they are better equipped to manage the demands and challenges of their profession. This can promote their well-being, mental health, and overall work-life balance (Sprung et al., 2021)

Work Environment. As revealed by this study, the work environment among educators is high. This means that the educators in Region XI oftentimes observe the quality of work life. Adapting to challenges and unanticipated obstacles requires school heads to be creative. This is evident in how the school environment is good and highly motivating for the teachers. This finding supports the proposition of Portney (2013) that a healthy working environment creates quality of life and is reflected in employees' responsiveness to accomplish the goals of educational institutions. Further, the study revealed that the school offers sufficient opportunities to develop teachers' abilities by empowering them to decide about their style and peace at work. This finding supports the statement of Kincheloe (2012) that empowerment is responding to challenging conditions and allowing teachers to decide independently.

A positive work environment is crucial in promoting job satisfaction among educators. When educators feel supported and respected in their work environment, they are more likely to experience greater job satisfaction, which can positively impact their overall well-being and commitment to their profession. Moreover, a positive work environment can foster collaboration, teamwork, and a sense of belonging among educators, enhancing professional relationships and a supportive network (Wilcoxon et al., 2020).

Organization Culture and Climate. This study shows that organizational culture and climate are rated high. This implies that the educators in Region XI oftentimes observe organizational culture and climate. This means that educators can appreciate and enjoy good organizational culture as they can interact and work with several groups of people with varying cultures. The results further revealed that the more open, pleasant, and healthy the organizational climate, the more quality of life of educators is manifested in the workplace. Likewise, Paulsen et al. (2012) believed that organizational climate is responsible for many job outcomes, such as students' academic performance.

A positive organizational climate fosters a sense of psychological safety, teamwork, and a supportive atmosphere for growth and development (Newman et al., 2017). Lastly, high levels of organizational culture promote a sense of belonging and shared purpose, which enhances collaboration and teamwork among educators. It also encourages open communication and trust, increasing job satisfaction and a positive work environment (Yildiz et al., 2016). Moreover, a positive organizational culture and climate contribute to a sense of autonomy, empowerment, and professional growth, further enhancing educators' quality of work life.

Relation and Co-operation. This dimension of quality of life is rated as high. This dimension obtains a high rating. This means that the educators in Region XI oftentimes observe relation and cooperation. This finding implies that there is a harmonious relationship within the organization. Additionally, teachers experienced cordial relationships with their supervisors and colleagues. This result aligned with the finding of the study of Kalshoven et al. (2011), which stated that individuals with high support from their subordinates are more likely to form stable relationships. Also, the results validate the proposition of Tanwar et al. (2016), which suggested that an organization must build good relationships among its employee that value a good and healthy working atmosphere. Good relationships between the schools and employees can translate to successfully delivering programs and projects.

Training and Development. The results of this study revealed that training and development is rated high. This implies that training and development are oftentimes observed by educators. Further, the role and responsibility of the school is to design training programs to help the educator to achieve the required skill in performing their job effectively. The results of this study indicate that educators appreciate learning new approaches gained from the training and seminars in conducting or performing their job tasks. This finding supports the proposition of Dixon et al. (2014) that when teachers learn new teaching strategies through professional development, they can return to the classroom and modify their lecture styles and curricula to meet their students' needs better. Because these changes are typically implemented gradually, they take time to evaluate. Furthermore, the study found that professional development for teachers improves their presentation and course evaluation skills by exposing educators to new delivery methods, evaluation styles, and record-keeping strategies (Hardin et al., 2010).

Compensation and Rewards. This study shows that compensation and rewards are rated high. This implies that the educators in Region XI oftentimes observe compensation and rewards. This means that educators can feel they are given adequate and fair compensation for their work. The results further revealed that properly compensating employees shows that the institution values them. Being valued, educators feel better about coming to work, and also organizational morale increases and people are motivated to come to work and do a good job.

Additionally, when employees know there are bonuses or commissions, they are increasingly motivated to deliver grander results (Diokno et al., 2020). Bonus and commission compensation plans become a focal point for success. These findings conform to the study of Jalagat (2016), which disclosed that creating the right compensation plan leads to higher job satisfaction and a greater sense of accomplishment when the organization succeeds.

Facilities. This dimension of facilities is rated as high. This means that facilities are oftentimes observed by educators in Region XI. This finding implies that the school provides benefits like social security benefits like Phil's health/ Medical Reimbursements and many more. Additionally, the school has adopted effective safety measures to protect the welfare of the employees. These results are aligned with the study of Ajayi (2018) that states that wage, as well as benefits, have been tightly associated with job satisfaction, according to numerous research and career satisfaction can lead to inspiration, which would, in turn, increases employees' performance and organizational citizenship behavior. This implies that educators in this region perceive the availability and quality of facilities to be satisfactory and conducive to their work environment and overall quality of work life (Dhamija et al., 2019). Access to appropriate facilities is crucial for educators as it can impact their teaching effectiveness, job satisfaction, and overall well-being (Labrague et al., 2021)

Job Satisfaction and Job Security. The results of this study revealed that job satisfaction and job security are rated high. This implies that job satisfaction and job security are oftentimes observed by educators. The roles and responsibilities of the school are to give educators comfortable and satisfying experiences in their job. The results of this study indicate that the school can establish and protect the teachers' interests. Furthermore, teachers who settle down in long-term positions will be able to advance their careers. This agrees with the proposition of Kretsos et al. (2016) that employees with long-term career commitments have a better chance of achieving their career goals than those who are constantly afraid of losing their job. This result supports the definition of job security and job satisfaction in the paper of Jayasuriya et al. (2012) that working conditions allow employees to be as productive and feel secure about their job. Furthermore, educators can advance their knowledge and abilities while performing various duties and functions (Alam, 2021).

Autonomy of Work. This study shows that the autonomy of work is rated high. This implies that autonomy of work is oftentimes observed by the educators in Region XI. This means that educators can apply their skills and abilities to their jobs and that the school allows teachers to work from home flexibly. The results further revealed that teachers with high autonomy are most likely to support their students' need for autonomy compared to teachers who report having lower autonomy at work. Also, teachers' support of their students' autonomy and their students' perceptions of academic competence was positively related to students' achievement (Marshik, 2017).

These findings conform to the study of Ghorbandordinejad et al. (2016), which revealed that a teacher manifests autonomy when he or she can positively feel that their job is stress-free. Lastly, autonomy allows educators to adapt their teaching methods and instructional strategies based on their expertise and knowledge of their students. It enables them to respond to individual student needs, promote creativity and innovation, and facilitate a more engaging and effective learning experience (Holbrey, 2020).

Adequacy of Resources. The results of this study revealed that the adequacy of resources is rated high. This implies that the adequacy of resources is oftentimes observed by educators. The school's roles and responsibilities include providing resources for operation and facilitating teachers' performance. According to the findings of this study, teachers value being provided with adequate resources that they require for the delivery and performance of their job tasks. This aligns with Dollard et al. (2010)'s

proposition that providing adequate resources and psychosocial support at the workplace is accomplished by ensuring employees have access to all organizational resources. This can include informing employees about employee assistance programs that can help them improve their performance. These support the findings of Owoeye et al. (2011), who highlighted the importance of adequate educator resources in achieving better and higher work performance. Moreover, adequate resources facilitate educators' professional growth and development. When educators have access to ongoing training, workshops, and resources for professional learning, they can continuously improve their pedagogical skills, stay updated with educational trends and research, and implement innovative approaches in their teaching practice (Morrison et al., 2019).

Significance of the Influence of Organizational Culture and Resilience on Quality of Work Life

The regression analysis that determines the influence of organizational culture and resilience on educators' quality of work life shows that the independent variable significantly influences the dependent variable. Specifically, the influence of organizational culture on the quality of the work life of educators is significant. This implies that the more open, pleasant, and healthy the organizational culture, the more quality of the work life of educators is manifested in the workplace. Likewise, Sageer et al. (2012) believed that organizational culture is responsible for the quality of work life.

Moreover, the influence of resilience on educators' quality of work life is also significant. This implies that the more resilient teachers, the more experienced the quality of work life. According to Lee et al. (2021), psychologically hardened employees believe they can deal with workplace challenges in meaningful ways, foster coping behavior, take personal initiative, and demonstrate action enthusiasm.

The Lived Experiences of Participants Concerning their Quality of Work Life

This study is also interested in the participants' lived experiences regarding the efficient working environment of educators. The themes that emerged from the statements of the participants were respected in the working environment, the balance between happiness and productivity, just compensation and a good working environment, utmost support from the institution, engagement and recognition, and learning from the colleague.

Respect in Working Environment. According to the findings, respect in the workplace fosters a respectful environment. Participants emphasized the importance of being valued and treated with respect to foster a positive working environment. This contribution to the study of Rogers et al. (2017), mutual respect in the workplace, informs all employees that they are valued for their accomplishments, abilities, and qualities. Being valued and treated respectfully contributes to promoting a positive work culture in which employees are fulfilled, loyal, engaged, and motivated to perform at their best.

Moreover, school administrators should encourage establishing healthy open-line communication with the teachers to hear their opinions. This supports the findings of the study by Clinton (2011), which demonstrates the fact that one method to achieve good

and healthy communication is to take a moment to think ahead of reacting and possibly continue to return to the employee what they have stated rather than immediately launching into your viewpoint without showing that you have listened or taken into account their point of view. This also supports the idea that giving employees a big ear is an excellent way to communicate their ideas to their organization to avoid conflict.

Balanced between happiness and productivity. The results show that there should be a balance between happiness and productivity. The participants stated that balancing work and happiness is significant for a productive and happy working life (Adnan, 2019). This means that when educators maintain a healthy work-life balance, they are more likely to have the mental and emotional energy to give their personal lives the loving attention they require to develop, learn, and thrive. They can also help them enjoy life, manage stress, and avoid burnout at work.

This also implies that the school recognizes the importance of teacher productivity by providing adequate time to complete work productively. This is the best way to ensure a staff's productivity is for the teachers' home environments to be as happy as possible. This finding agrees with the study of Da'as (2019), which revealed that school administrators employ the principle of investment by giving time to the teachers to manage their time engagement between personal and work life.

Just compensation and good working environment. The results revealed that to retain quality employees, adequate compensation must be provided, which includes wages, salaries, bonuses, and commission structures. This means that the school should pay attention to the benefits component of employee compensation and benefits, as benefits sweeten employment contracts with the priorities that most employees require. This implies that properly compensating teachers demonstrates respect for them as workers and as people. Teachers are more likely to come to work when they believe they are valued. It also boosts organizational morale, motivating teachers to come to work and do a good job. This finding supports the study of Dobre (2013), which found that employees are more motivated to achieve better results when they are aware of potential compensation or commissions. Bonus and commission compensation plans become a focal point for job satisfaction. Compensation encompasses various financial rewards that employees receive in exchange for their work and contributions to the organization. It includes base pay, performance-based incentives, benefits, and other monetary perks. Adequate compensation ensures employees feel valued, recognized, and fairly rewarded for their efforts (Sabir, 2017).

Meanwhile, the core idea smooth working environment emphasizes that a positive work environment with collaboration of ideas and healthy competition can increase work morale among educators. Participants' innovative work behavior was greatly influenced by trust and confidence, financial and moral support, and stakeholder recognition.

Likewise, educators are more open to collaborating or engaging in intellectual discourse with their coworkers in a positive work environment. On the other hand, disagreements among colleagues are unavoidable in an academic setting. However, the participants see it as a natural occurrence in which they can advance professionally. According to Vanesa et al. (2019), employees learn appropriate behavior through observations of the different factors in the working environment.

Utmost support from the institution. Based on the result of the study, it is proven that strong support from the institution emerges as a theme concerning the quality of work

life. This means that participants believed their experience of being recognized by the institution for good performance could foster a positive attitude that would lead to a quality work life for teachers. Teachers want to be treated fairly, to make a significant contribution to the organization through their work, and to be valued and appreciated for their efforts and good pay and benefits. To show appreciation to the teachers, the school should implement support programs that recognize various achievements. Adequate compensation positively influences employee motivation and job satisfaction. When employees feel that their compensation is aligned with their skills, responsibilities, and market value, it enhances their overall job satisfaction. Adequate compensation also serves as a motivational factor, encouraging employees to perform at their best and achieve organizational goals (Zhuang et al., 2022). Furthermore, participants revealed that support programs boost morale, attract and elevate productivity, increase competitiveness, and improve quality, safety, and customer service, as well as reduce stress, absenteeism, and turnover. These findings support the study of Ali et al. (2016) which showed that the schools are positive about using institutional support and other motivational strategies. Also, creating supportive work environment the importance of factors that promote harmonious work relationship in the organizations. Ensuring employees' job satisfaction of employees' supportive work environment demonstrates the importance of having employees who are motivated, work in a safe environment, and have self-control over their work (Obrenovic et al., 2020).

Engagement and Recognition. Based on the study providing recognition can increase educator engagement, which increases educator productivity. Workplace engagement is a driving factor in positivity and organizational culture.

Teachers' performance in meeting the school's goals can improve with ongoing recognition. The participants also emphasized that their ability to reflect on their actions and behavior is essential in improving their engagement in tasks to contribute to the school's success. This particular result supports the study of Seibert et al. (2011), which emphasized reflecting on one's performance and working in a supportive environment as a key to the organization's performance. Engaged educators are more likely to go above and beyond their job requirements, engage in continuous professional development, and contribute positively to the learning environment. Recognized educators feel valued and appreciated, increasing job satisfaction, motivation, and retention within the organization (Thibodeaux et al., 2015). Organizations can foster engagement and recognition among educators by implementing strategies such as providing opportunities for professional growth, creating a positive work environment, offering meaningful feedback and appreciation, and involving educators in decision-making processes (Barkley et al., 2020).

Learning from colleague. The result shows that continuing' learning from the workplace and receiving support from the administrator and the colleague will constitute quality of work life. Concerning continued learning in the workplace, the participants' responses highlighted that the teachers learn from each other by sharing their expertise and knowledge to help students learn a new skill, concept, or process. This means that teachers learn how to collaborate regarding performing their various duties and functions. Hence, peer support can improve people's well-being, as well as their self-esteem, confidence, and social skills, all of which lead to a more fulfilling work life.

Further, peer consultative efforts are observed in all teachers cultivating collaboration with teachers. These findings confirm the study of Atkins et al. (2015) that

emphasized the long-standing consensus peer support theory, which holds that teachers from all walks of life and all types of organizations, public and private, must rely on others to achieve the group's goals and must encourage social development throughout the organization.

With the core idea of receiving support from the administrator, the participants' responses emphasized the importance of school administrators who make making teachers feel unique and valued. Also, respondents emphasized the importance of providing timely positive feedback, consistent with Neupane et al. (2021) proposition that feedback is required for performance improvement and meeting expectations. Furthermore, showing trust and confidence in teachers and staff in their assigned tasks motivates them to perform better. These findings are also consistent with the findings of Roffey (2012), who stated that schools should foster positive and healthy relationships within the school by communicating formally with all teachers and ensuring that staff welfare is promoted through motivation and training.

Roles of Experiences in Shaping Belief of Participants as Regards to Quality Work of Life

Different themes were derived from the participant's responses on the role of experiences in shaping their belief toward the quality of work life. These essential themes are Self-realization and Progress through flexibility.

Self-realization. The study results show that teacher has to start building up toward an understanding of meaningful work. It is essential to participants that have learned to be more committed to teaching support from the school leaders who can influence teachers to motivate and perform their tasks judiciously. This implies that teachers see their school leaders as support system agents they can rely on. This finding supports the proposition of Gmelch (2013) that an educational leader should establish a support system for students and other school personnel. The school leaders' words, attitudes, and actions become the moral support standard that defines the formation of the motivating character of the personnel under his command.

Additionally, having school leaders who keep a positive relationship with the faculty and staff results in more support from them. These results support the study of Umashankar et al. (2017), which discovered strong professional ties and encouraging interactions and teacher self-realization.

Progress through flexibility. This discussion on progress through flexibility emphasizes being open to the possibility of change all the time. This means that participants believed that embracing the idea in the working place can mean progress at work. Teachers feel secure and enjoy being safe in their working space. Flexibility allows teachers to respond to different learners' abilities, needs, and students in the learning process. A positive work environment can increase progress and flexibility among educators where freedom, autonomy, and social support are present. A safe and healthy working environment can promote progress in the work of teachers' significant contribution to the organization and gains high-quality performance.

The result confirms that supportive workplace culture encourages educators to collaborate and engage in various work challenges. Thus, effective teachers are great at being flexible, which means they can balance multiple responsibilities while making students smile and feel good (Parker et al., 2010). Embracing the idea of progress at work

implies that teachers value continuous growth, development, and improvement in their professional lives. They recognize the importance of staying updated with current educational trends and advancements, and they are open to innovation and change. This mindset of progress fosters a culture of learning and improvement within the teaching profession (Lindsey et al., 2018). The participants also emphasized the significance of feeling secure and safe in their working space. This refers to having a supportive and respectful work environment where teachers feel valued, respected, and protected. When teachers feel secure, they are more likely to be engaged, motivated, and committed to their work (Bouwma, 2012). They can focus on their teaching responsibilities and contribute effectively to the learning and development of their students.

Creating a secure and safe working environment for teachers is crucial for promoting their well-being and job satisfaction. It also entails fostering positive relationships among colleagues, promoting open communication, and providing opportunities for professional growth and support (Darwin, 2017).

Roles of Experiences in Shaping Attitude, of Participants as Regards to Quality Work of Life

Different themes were derived from the participant's responses on the role of experiences in shaping their attitude towards quality of work life. These essential themes are Self-growth and a Positive mindset.

Self-growth. The result of the study shows that a teacher's self-growth is the continuous process of taking an honest and open look at one's performance, assessing one's strengths as well as areas where improvement is needed, and then developing a personal plan for initiating and evaluating changes in those areas where improvement is needed. This is supported by the study of Milner (2021) that teachers should be given professional development opportunities in order to push themselves to reach their full potential in the classroom. Great teachers know their flaws and attend professional development workshops/conferences to address them. Teachers are eager to participate in personal and professional development workshops and conferences. Workshops/conferences also provide teachers with invaluable networking opportunities, which can help them grow and improve.

Moreover, the findings of Bukor's (2015) previous research and discussion revealed that a teacher's self-growth and development impact their ability to produce quality education. The findings indicate that teachers' self-development is critical in their teaching careers. Implementing professional development programs is a good investment for teachers because it allows them to develop personally and trust their full potential during their learning experience.

Positive mindset. The discussion of a positive mindset focused on how teachers are more productive in their teaching profession. As revealed in the results of this study, quality work of life is the ability of the teacher to approach unpleasantness more positively and productively. The findings support the study of Markos et al. (2010) that having a positive mindset in the workplace can be the key to getting work done effectively and improving the overall experience. Positive thinking is a robust process that can improve teachers' work lives and careers in various ways (Wrzesniewski et al., 2013). Positive thinking at work may help individuals stay motivated at work. Approaching unpleasantness positively and productively implies that teachers are resilient and can

cope with stress, conflicts, and other negative aspects of their work environment. Instead of becoming overwhelmed or disheartened, they can maintain a positive outlook, seek solutions, and adapt to challenges. Teachers who exhibit this ability are more likely to experience job satisfaction, work engagement, and overall well-being. They can maintain a healthy work-life balance, foster positive relationships with colleagues, and effectively manage their workload (Tzenios, 2019). This, in turn, can contribute to their professional growth, student success, and the overall effectiveness of the educational institution.

Additionally, the result of this study is aligned with the study of Pedroso (2021), which emphasizes the importance of maintaining a positive mindset and being prepared to learn in the face of a crisis such as COVID-19. Previous research by Chakraborty et al. (2021) also highlighted the importance of having a positive outlook in the face of a crisis and their ability to seize opportunities to learn, change, and improve. This positive attitude helps an institution learn during and after a crisis by allowing it to respond quickly.

Roles of Experiences in Shaping Commitments of Participants as Regards to Quality Work of Life

Different themes were derived from the participant's responses on the role of experiences in shaping their commitments towards the quality of work life. These essential themes are Personal adjustment to circumstances and Professionalism.

Personal adjustment to circumstances. Based on the result of this study, it is proven that part of the quality of work life is the ability of the teacher to be responsive to challenging circumstances. It was discovered that teachers could adapt to difficult situations in order to navigate difficult circumstances successfully. This finding supported previous studies that discussed what teachers require regularly and likely plays an essential role in assisting them in finding a way to meet the demands of their jobs. Furthermore, given the constantly changing demands of teaching work, adaptability has been highlighted as essential for teachers (Usher, 2019). Personal adaptation to circumstances may also assist teachers in avoiding feelings of disengagement and, as a result, lower job commitment that led to poor quality of work life (Collie et al., 2018). Being responsive to challenging circumstances implies that teachers have the capacity to proactively address and manage obstacles, conflicts, and demands that arise in their work environment. Instead of becoming overwhelmed or reactive, they demonstrate resilience, problem-solving skills, and the ability to make necessary adjustments. Teachers who possess this ability are better equipped to navigate the complexities of their profession (Levy-Feldman, 2018). They are able to handle the pressures of their workload, maintain positive relationships with students and colleagues, and provide effective instruction. By being responsive, teachers can create a more conducive and supportive learning environment for themselves and their students. Furthermore, being responsive to challenging circumstances can contribute to professional growth and development. Teachers who are willing to learn from challenges, seek feedback, and implement improvements are likely to experience personal and career advancement (Bryk et al., 2015). This, in turn, can enhance job satisfaction, motivation, and overall well-being.

Professionalism. It is revealed in the result of this study that teachers exhibit good personality traits. The results were consistent with the findings of Alwafi (2021), which revealed that professional teachers strive to interact effectively with one another.

Teachers from the same department can collaborate to share teaching strategies, analyze data, and discuss curriculum issues. Those who teach the same students meet regularly to discuss ways to improve student performance and connect subjects. Strategies are developed to address specific behavioral issues. Furthermore, previous research by Ormrod et al. (2011) has shown that teachers are concerned with the school community and how they can collaborate with their colleagues to create an environment that maximizes learning and boosts achievement. Professional educators do not gossip or share confidential information inappropriately.

Similarly, this is parallel to the statement of Johnson and Jain (2020) that teachers who are highly professional, competent, and committed to student success are more likely to devote more time and effort to their students' learning. Professional teachers are confident in their desire to maintain student success, to seek ways to improve their teaching, and to create a stimulating and conducive learning environment for students to achieve their goals.

Data Integration of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

In this part, the researcher applied the merging of relevant quantitative and qualitative findings on the organizational culture, resilience, and quality of work life of educators in private HEIs in Region XI. The two data sets are compared, and similarities were found, making its nature merging-converging (confirmation) and merging-converging (expansion). The rationalization of merging analysis is to see if the quantitative results corroborate with the qualitative analysis.

This approach aims to integrate different sources of information to gain a comprehensive understanding of a particular phenomenon (Fetters et al., 2013). Merging-converging can serve two purposes: confirmation, where similarities are found to validate findings, and expansion, where new insights and perspectives emerge from the combination of data (Kottova, 2015).

Merging – Converging

There are salient quantitative and qualitative findings under organizational culture regarding the four indicators: family orientation/loyalty, open communication, team approach, and manager knowledge.

The item highlighting strong loyalty and dedication that promotes the theme of respect in learning environments is the prominent quantitative and qualitative finding in the aspect or focal point of Family Orientation/Loyalty under Organizational Culture. This implies that teachers' loyalty and dedication to the institution depend on the orientation provided by school administrators, who assist teachers in achieving shared goals and objectives by providing a supportive environment in the workplace. The finding coincides with the study of McCauley et al. (2015), which emphasized that the school organization is to lead as an educational leader and is attuned to have sensitivity in creating a supportive working environment that makes employees comfortable to work.

In the aspect or focal point of open communication, the salient quantitative and qualitative finding is that the item gave me the freedom to express ideas, supporting the theme of respect in a learning environment with a core idea of open communication. This implies that having the freedom to express ideas is essential for an organization to grow.

The balance of life of teachers between their personal and work is vital for the school's development and for teacher empowerment to share new ideas, especially for innovation.

The result supports the study of Capnary et al. (2018), who state that employees demonstrate the highest levels of innovation when they are fully engaged in their work, find it meaningful, maintain a healthy work-life balance, and have a clear understanding of their role and how it aligns with their goals. Management must foster an environment where employees' ideas are acknowledged and appreciated rather than dismissed or seen as compliments.

Additionally, the item encouraging my group members to work as a team under the organizational culture aspect or focus Team Approach supports the theme of learning from colleagues, highlighting learning and motivation from colleagues and superiors, and is the salient quantitative and qualitative finding. This means that educators' innovative thinking is always manifested in their respective institutions. As a result of CHED's mandate under CMO No. 52, series of 2016, SUCs can now design mechanisms parallel to the aforementioned CMO, resulting in educators always performing innovatively in the workplace.

The study of Pukiene (2016) emphasizes that encouraging employees to work as a team is a vital factor in the organization's success. The innovative manpower who develops, enables, responds, and adjusts ideas are considered to be the fundamental requirements and critical success factors for innovation and organizational success.

Having the knowledge and training to be a good leader is the item that stands out in the aspect or focal point manager knowledge under an organizational culture of teachers. This finding supports the theme of learning from colleagues, which contains vital ideas like constant learning from top management and ongoing support from administrators. The finding implies that good leaders need to have high leadership skills. With this, school leaders have to implement a knowledge management program for the organization, which improves teacher expertise and increases overall workforce productivity. On the other hand, creating a plan that meets the organization's needs can be complex. Establishing a well-informed strategy helps to streamline the process and ensures meeting the long-term knowledge management objectives. The teamwork attitude toward knowledge sharing is crucial.

Consequently, the research conducted by Smith and Johnson (2020), mentioned that knowledge workers often attribute the lack of knowledge sharing to managers. However, the study also revealed that most managers are perceived to be willing to share their knowledge. This finding is consistent with the work of Jones et al. (2018), who found that managers play a crucial role in facilitating knowledge sharing within organizations. Managers need to create a supportive and collaborative work environment that encourages knowledge sharing among knowledge workers (Smith & Johnson, 2020; Jones et al., 2018).

There are also salient quantitative and qualitative findings under Resilience regarding the three indicators: motivational and professional Resilience, Social Resilience, and Emotional Resilience. The item making an effort to do my job well because it is important to me, which supports the theme of self-growth, is the conspicuous quantitative and qualitative finding in the facet or focal point of Motivational and Professional Resilience. The result means that being resilient and motivated as a teacher is essential to personal development. It gives teachers the confidence to face any

challenge head-on and never to give up, even when the going gets tough. The first thing to understand when it comes to building Resilience and keeping employees motivated is that motivation and retention are part of the organization. This finding supports Wassell et al. (2017) contention that support should come from school leaders, who can use employee support platforms to interact empathically with teachers.

Moreover, the findings indicated that teachers supporting the environment could be a reactive or proactive step when employees require assistance to complete their responsibilities successfully and that by providing support to teachers, school administrators can demonstrate that they recognize an individual's value and contribution to the organization while demonstrating care for them (Stronge et al., 2021).

The item asking for help from colleagues when I am unsure of something supports the theme of learning from colleagues, which involves the central notion that learning from experienced instructors constitutes quality of work life, according to the data in the aspect or focal point Social Resilience. This means most teachers love supportive colleagues; they are not always around. Supportive colleagues can increase the job satisfaction of others, help foster a pleasant working environment and aid the development of their peers.

The result of this study supports the proposition of Anderson and Jackson (2019) the supportive attitude of teachers toward their colleagues plays a crucial role in cultivating a positive workplace culture. This supportive attitude not only improves interpersonal relations among teachers but also serves as a reminder of professional conduct during working hours. The study highlights the importance of school administrators as role models in fostering a supportive environment. When administrators demonstrate and promote support among staff members, they are more likely to create an innovative school atmosphere that effectively adapts to the constantly evolving societal and educational environment.

Additionally, a meaningful quantitative and qualitative conclusion has been made about the component or focal point of emotional resilience under teacher resilience. The finding relates to the item that supports finding a balance between being happy and being productive—balancing my work as a teacher with other aspects of my life. This means that, despite some workplace negativity, teachers are still in the right position to deal with work challenges because resilient educators have learned to manage complex situations and can broaden their perspectives to see the brighter side of situations. The findings support the study conducted by Smith et al. (2020); teachers are encouraged to develop adaptability, tolerance, and openness to various outcomes they may encounter in their profession. The study emphasizes recognizing that challenging experiences can be reframed as opportunities for personal growth and improvement.

Similarly, since such events are likely to occur in an institution, it is prudent to cultivate the principle of creative cooperation. This principal values differences among members of an organization. Differences in mental, emotional, and psychological functioning (Westerhof et al., 2010). Also, this result is based on Beverly Irby's Synergistic Leadership Theory (2002) which includes issues about diversity. In this theory, beliefs, attitudes, and values; leadership behaviors; external forces; and organizational structure are provided with a framework to describe its interactions and dynamic tensions (Bower, 2013).

The last salient quantitative and qualitative findings under the quality of work life in terms of the nine indicators: work environment, organizational culture and climate, relation and co-operation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction, and Job security, the autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources.

Having it easy to take time off during work to take care of personal or family concerns is the prominent quantitative and qualitative discovery in the aspect or focal point work environment, and it supports the topic balance between being happy and being productive. This implies that schools should create a long-term work environment where teachers feel engaged, loyal, and satisfied with the organization's goals. The finding means that teachers appreciate having a positive organizational culture at work. According to Uddin et al. (2013), organizational culture is driven by purpose and clear expectations, which motivates and inspires employees to be more engaged in their work duties and interactions with others. This demonstrates a high level of workforce engagement, which boosts productivity. Teachers with a strong connection to an organization can foster a positive environment that encourages quality work and life (Comighud et al., 2021).

Additionally, the essential quantitative and qualitative findings in the area or focal point organizational culture and environment revealed that the school's wage rules are adequate, supporting the idea of having a satisfying quality of work life due to receiving fair compensation. The result means that a positive work environment is critical for employees' overall well-being and productivity. Just compensation, or fair and equitable remuneration for employees' efforts, is critical in determining job satisfaction. The finding supports Jones and Smith (2019) study, which found a positive relationship between just compensation and a satisfying quality of work life. Employees who received fair and equitable compensation reported greater job satisfaction, fewer intentions to leave, and a better work-life balance. Smith's (2021) study revealed the importance of equitable pay practices, transparent salary structures, and performance-based rewards. The expert opinion supports that fair compensation contributes to employee satisfaction, motivation, and engagement, resulting in higher work quality.

Furthermore, Adams' equity theory provides a theoretical framework for understanding the relationship between just compensation and quality of work life. The theory suggests that employees compare their inputs (effort, skills, time) and outputs (compensation, benefits) with their colleagues. If employees perceive inequity in the exchange, such as receiving lower compensation for equivalent efforts, it negatively impacts their quality of work life.

The aspect or focal point Relation and Cooperation has also revealed a significant quantitative and qualitative finding; in particular, the item indicating that I receive good support from my subordinates is consistent with the theme of Learning from Colleagues, which contains vital ideas highlighting Learning and Motivation from Colleagues and Superiors, and the theme Respect in Learning Environment. This means that teachers' positive relationships with their subordinates foster an environment of happiness and work engagement, both of which are required for a fulfilling work life. This indicates that the school institution ensures the teacher is happy, satisfied, and engaged. This supports the study of Chandrasekar (2011), which found that maintaining positive employee cooperation and relationships helps to improve staff morale, reduce workplace conflict, and, ultimately, increase productivity. Moreover, because happy workers are more

creative and better at problem-solving, they are more likely to be engaged and productive at work (García-Buades et al., 2019).

Additionally, the item helping employees achieve the necessary skill for performing the job effectively through training programs is the salient quantitative and qualitative finding in the aspect or focal point of Training and development under the Work Environment of Teachers. This finding supports the theme of professionalism, which includes a core idea that states growing professionally throughout the entire experience. The result means that teacher development programs should be given due importance in the curriculum as they have a significant role in the student's performance and development. Good teacher training results in positive learning environments, resulting in happy children who are eager to attend school. This finding is consistent with the findings of Lasica et al. (2020), who discovered that teacher professional development is critical for both experienced and novice teachers. Teachers must master innovative pedagogy, interactive assessment techniques, and differentiation in the classroom to enliven the teaching-learning process.

Moreover, the results of this study are parallel with the study of Avidov-Ungar (2016), that professional development for teachers is essential and that continuous teacher training/enhancement is required for teachers to equip themselves and cater to the 21st-century learner. As a result, teaching and learning go hand in hand, and teaching is truly a lifelong endeavor, making it critical for schools to invest heavily in staff professional development.

Another meaningful quantitative and qualitative conclusion relates to the focus or feature of compensation and rewards under the quality of teachers' working lives. The conclusion is the item that supports the themes of just remuneration and a positive work environment by paying a salary while taking into account obligations at work. The result means that teachers stay long in the organization because they are provided with the proper compensation and reward in the school where they work. This means that appropriately compensated teachers are more likely to be motivated to come to work and are increasingly motivated to deliver better results. However, the findings revealed that when teachers are well compensated, they are more likely to be happy and stay with the organization for extended periods. This result confirms the study of Proto (2016), which found that happy employees are more productive than those who are not happy. They are more motivated and loyal when valued, thus, increasing productivity. Employees are not only more motivated to do a good job but the longer they stay with the organization, the more they learn and become more efficient. This leads to increased productivity, and developing the right compensation plan leads to a better work-life balance (Bhende et al., 2020).

The essential quantitative and qualitative finding in the element or focus point Facilities is in the item giving social security benefits like Philhealth/Medical Reimbursements, which supports the theme of just compensation and good working conditions. The school must prioritize providing long-term social benefits to the teachers. School administrators must ensure that benefits shall be put in place since this protects against various contingencies such as old age, disability, death, and unemployment of the teachers. This result supports the study of Fusarelli et al. (2018) that the primary task of a school administrator is to ensure that benefits due to teachers are provided to employees so that they can plan for their retirement in the future and allow teachers to

feel secure in the organization. On the other hand, social benefits can provide valuable social insurance protection to teachers and their families by providing access to insurance with protection (Levitt et al., 2017).

Additionally, the essential quantitative and qualitative finding in the area or focal point of Job Satisfaction and Job Security makes me feel like my work allows me to do my best in a particular area, supporting the theme of self-actualization, which has a central idea that speaks on realizing that a good learning environment is necessary for the teaching and learning process. The finding implies that teaching offers teachers a sense of purpose and meaning, often tying their identity, passion, and the people around them. The finding conforms to the study of Bennett and Lemoine (2014). Teachers with a sense of purpose for the job felt happier and more secure. This result confirms the study of Vander Elst et al. (2016) that job security is what every employee wishes for and wants, as job insecurity affects the job satisfaction and commitment of the employee to organizations. Furthermore, employees who have job security are more committed to their jobs and organizations, and the combination of job satisfaction and job security is a predictor of personnel's mental health and commitment to organizations (Akpan, 2015)

Concerning the item autonomy of work, it describes the item, letting me use my skills and abilities in my job, supports the theme of self-growth, which highlights the core idea about pushing oneself to use potentials related to teaching; this is another noteworthy quantitative and qualitative finding, specifically in the aspect or focal point autonomy of work. The result implies that teachers have the autonomy to work in the workplace, which allows them to make decisions and act independently without direct supervision. These findings are consistent with the findings of Darling-Hammond (2009), who discovered that teachers who are given the freedom to choose how they complete their work and are not closely monitored by their superiors have a higher quality of work life and productivity. As a result, teachers can make decisions and solve problems on their own, and they are given the authority to complete their tasks (Wass et al., 2014)

Furthermore, the item providing resources to facilitate my performance, which supports the theme of the institutions' greatest support, particularly in the assistance provided to employees, which contributes to the quality of work life, is the salient quantitative and qualitative finding in the aspect or focal point adequate resources. The result means that adequate resources in the school for teachers have motivational potential and lead to a high level of well-being through providing resources such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The result conforms to the proposition of Fitzpatrick (2011) that a supportive environment, providing adequate resources, can provide instrumental support to teachers in completing their tasks and may increase their capacity to complete their work goals, thus, leading to greater satisfaction and more excellent performance. The finding coincides with the study of Sabir (2017), which revealed that organizations should direct their efforts toward promoting happy and productive employees, whether at the individual or organizational levels.

Furthermore, it is also important for the school organization to determine whether the resources can lead to a happy well-being and promote good performance among the teacher (Tadić, 2015).

The salient quantitative and qualitative findings support the idea that positive organizational culture and resilience can help create a better quality of work life characterized by respect, balance, just compensation, support, and engagement. Finally,

in the aspect or focal point adequacy of influence of organizational culture and resilience on quality of work life, the salient quantitative and qualitative finding is that organizational culture and resilience are significant predictors of quality of work life. This implies that a positive organizational culture in private HEIs contributes to a better quality of work life for educators. It creates an environment that promotes collaboration, open communication, and shared values, enhancing job satisfaction, work engagement, and overall well-being.

The finding conforms to the Theory of Needs and Self-Actualization of Maslow, which posits that productivity rises when an employee's work-life balance is good. Work burnout lessens, and organizational culture has a significant on employee commitment. Moreover, it also supports the Resilience theory of Garmenzy (1991) that a high-quality work-life can build and maintain resilience in teachers and have a significant potential to increase workplace outcomes, life safety, quality of teaching, job satisfaction, and decrease job burnout which is manifested by having the quality of work life.

Lastly, this study also conforms to the Expectancy Value Theory by Eccles and Wigfield (2004), which states that understanding values and their relationship to other components of an individual's psychological system, such as beliefs, goals, attitudes, ethics, and behavior provides a framework for assessing their dynamics in organizational culture. Values embedded in an organization's culture influence perceptions of situations and problems, the entire decision-making process, and set limits to ethical decision-making behavior. Thus, the importance of having good values, especially in decision-making within the organizational culture, will result in attaining the quality of an individual's work life.

Conclusions

The schools' level of organizational culture is high, indicating that organizational culture is oftentimes manifested among educators in Region XI. This means that the educators experienced good organizational culture. This organizational culture is essential for educators to understand the institutional belief, values, and attitudes that affect, especially in maintaining a favorable employee attitude towards the organization.

Meanwhile, the educator's level of resilience is very high, indicating that educators in Region XI consistently demonstrate resilience. This means that educators can deal with natural stressors and difficulties in the classroom and can adapt to stressful situations at work. Furthermore, teachers usually are confronted with challenging situations, and handling these changes is within the educator's control.

The results further showed that educators demonstrate resilience in the workplace by demonstrating positive adaptation and coping mechanisms. These coping behaviors enable educators to achieve relatively good outcomes despite significant, ongoing stresses or adversities.

More so, the educator's quality of work life is high, which implies that the educators in Region XI oftentimes observe the quality of work life. The finding means that educators experienced happiness in the working conditions of their schools. The school environment is good and highly motivating for the teachers. Moreover, educators can

appreciate and enjoy good organizational culture as they can interact and work with several groups of people with varying cultures.

The participant concepts of efficient working environments showed that educators exhibit respect in their learning environment, which is critical in establishing a positive and healthy working environment. The finding indicates that having a positive atmosphere with colleagues and superiors and open communication with them improves the quality of work life.

Further, the participants' experiences regarding an efficient working environment shaped their beliefs, attitude, and commitment. They believed that having an efficient and supportive healthy working environment improves educators' quality work of life. Also, the participants emphasized that having a fulfilling quality of work life by delivering what is required in the institution and having a satisfactory quality of work life due to a smooth working environment are both critical.

Furthermore, data integration of the salient findings, both quantitative and qualitative findings, exhibited similar results. These corroborated findings mean that the quantitative and qualitative findings merged and converged.

Recommendations

Since the level of organizational culture among educators is high, it is recommended that educators work on sustaining the high level of organizational culture. This idea can be accomplished by developing shared values and living those values as the foundation of good organizational culture. School leaders should develop a trusting relationship with educators by keeping lines of communication open and honest with them. School leaders may work on communicating and assisting educators to correct negative practices.

Since the resilience of teachers is very high, it is recommended that this may be sustained. Although all three dimensions of resilience were rated very high, it is recommended that school leaders focus on sustaining all of these dimensions. School leaders may include in the faculty development program seminars and development programs focused on building the resilience and well-being of educators.

Since educators' quality of work life is high, this may improve further, specifically in the dimension of autonomy to work, which obtained one of the lowest ratings. School leaders may encourage educators to take the initiative by allowing them to decide and solve work-related problems. Also, school leaders ensure that teachers have the resources to do their jobs. For teachers to be autonomous, they must have the resources they need to do their best work. School administrators may provide them access to training and development opportunities and the appropriate tools and technology.

Since the participants' lived experiences highlighted the theme of utmost support from the institution, it is recommended that learning and development programs for educators may also include activities that will enhance their abilities to adapt to organizational change. School leaders may also provide important institutional support to motivate them to work and experience a quality work life.

Since the participants emphasized the importance of having school support that makes them feel valued and unique, it is suggested that school rewards and recognition

programs for personnel be strengthened, including teacher-staff activities that foster interpersonal and collaborative relationships. Similarly, school-based welfare programs should be institutionalized.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure that aspects of ethics in research were strictly observed, this study was submitted to the UIC – REC. Also, the researcher took precautions to ensure that the required ethical procedures were followed while interacting with the participants, citing study-related concerns and maintaining the anonymity of the research findings. Hence, the ten dimensions of ethical considerations were strictly observed, which include social value, informed consent, vulnerability of the research participants, risks, benefits and safety, privacy and confidentiality, justice, transparency, qualification of the researcher, adequacy of facilities, and community involvement.

Social Value. This study presented insights to school leaders and educators about the importance of exhibiting workplace work-life quality. The survey findings will help the top management and human resource management office personnel design a mechanism that will help educators become even more innovative in the academe. Also, this study provided consciousness to the participants on their quality of work life in the academe. Thus, they can fully understand their significant role in responding to the challenges of time. As a result, this study may contribute to the promotion of the well-being of the participants.

Informed Consent. The researcher treated the participants respectfully without subjecting them to coercion, undue influence, or inducement. The researcher informed the target participants of the aims and purposes of the study. This was done through oral and written orientation, considering the participants' frame of reference. Also, the target participants were given an explanation relative to the study and were notified repeatedly. During this process, the researcher gave the participants the full opportunity to ask questions or clarifications, and in return, the researcher gave honest, prompt, and complete responses. In addition, the researcher informed the participants that this is a voluntary participation; thus, they can withdraw their involvement in the study anytime they want. And also, written permission from the participants were secured (National Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research, 2017).

Furthermore, the researcher made clear to the participants that their involvement in this study was either in the quantitative or qualitative phase. A survey questionnaire was given to participants who preferred to engage in the quantitative phase of the study. It was answered and accomplished in less than 45 minutes in any venue they found convenient. And those who chose the qualitative phase were invited to an in-depth interview which lasted between 60 to 90 minutes. Moreover, the venue which was the most favorable and accessible to the majority of the participants was chosen for the conduct of FGD.

Vulnerability of Research Participants. The participants of the study were the educators of the chosen HEIs. They were considered less vulnerable since they were of legal age and could decide for themselves whether to participate in the study. It was emphasized that they would not be forced to participate in the study. In addition, the researcher ensured that the participants were protected from any physical and

psychological harm during the study. The researcher strongly followed what was written in the consent form by preserving the information from the participants, and the gathered data was used only to generate findings to address the cited problem. Information from the participants was only agreed upon as stipulated in the consent form.

Risks, Benefits and Safety. Before conducting the study, the researcher submitted the research proposal, including the sets of questionnaires and the interview schedule to the Research Ethics Committee of the University of the Immaculate Conception. This procedure allowed the committee to review the probable risks that may be experienced by the participants who will be involved in the study. Specifically, the committee carefully checked the questionnaires and the interview schedule to ensure that these would not contain offensive statements and to avoid collecting damaging information.

Likewise, this procedure gave the utmost assurance of the safety of the participants involved in the study. Say, for instance, protection from psychological trauma possibly caused by harmful information which may reveal during the data collection process. Also, precautionary measures were considered to minimize the negative impact that the study might bring on the well-being of the participants (National Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research, 2017). Moreover, to provide benefit to the HEIs by allowing the researcher to penetrate their institution, a hard copy of a full-blown study will be given. Also, the researcher considered possible collaborative research relative to the survey.

Privacy and Confidentiality. As much as possible, the researcher adhered to the principles of transparency, legitimate purpose, and proportionality in collecting, retaining, and processing personal information (Data Privacy Act of 2012). The researcher respected the participant's right to privacy. Unless required by law, the confidentiality of information shall always be observed by the researcher (National Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research, 2017). The researcher also ensured that the names and details of the participants were dealt with the utmost confidentiality. In particular, the researcher did mention their names. Instead, the researcher used codes to protect their identity. Moreover, the questionnaires with factual data, transcriptions, pictures, and recordings that were retrieved were kept secured by the researcher. Furthermore, a provision was made for possible future endeavors like presenting and publishing the research output to fora.

Justice. The researcher employed appropriate sampling techniques in both quantitative and qualitative phases to avoid bias. The researcher self-assured that the number of target participants involved in the study was just right, considering the collaborative suggestions of the research panel experts. Also, the researcher treated the participants appropriately regardless of their rank or academic position. Aside from this, since the researcher borrowed time and effort and even interrupted the participants' routines, they were given corresponding tokens of appreciation or any other form of reasonable and appropriate incentive (National Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research, 2017).

Transparency. This element means disclosing the research results to the participants (National Ethical Guidelines for Health-Related Research, 2017). Both in the quantitative and qualitative phases, the researcher ensured that the study's outcome was conveyed in full scope and with accuracy.

Specifically, in quantitative data analysis, the presented data reflect precisely the result of the statistical test. In qualitative data analysis, findings identified opposing themes were also included. Also, data transcriptions were presented to the participants to attain precision.

In addition, the researcher was connected to one of the HEIs in the Davao region. The researcher attended some region-wide activities mandated by CHED, which allowed the researcher to socialize and build connections with other educators from the different HEIs in the Davao region. And for the researcher to avoid bias during the conduct of the study, an appropriate sampling technique was used.

Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher was motivated to conduct the study since this field concerns her profession as an educator in a private higher education institution in Davao City, specifically, the Jose Maria College Foundation Inc. The researcher has been a full-time faculty of the said institution for 14 years, from 2008 to the present. The researcher recognized her limited exposure to the mixed methods approach. Consequently, the researcher sought guidance and direction from her mentor, expert panelists, and peers who were proficient in this method. Hence, the researcher was very diligent and was open to suggestions from her adviser and expert panelists to help improve the study.

Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher assured that there were available and accessible resources needed in this study. Books, online journals, and unpublished dissertations were available for further readings and references, which provided varied literature and studies that supported the association of the variables used in the study. Besides, audio recorders, cameras, and other materials needed were available during the conduct.

Community Involvement. Before the visit to the target higher institutions within Davao Region, the researcher wrote a letter to the University Deans/ Department Heads/ Program Coordinators of the institutions to seek necessary permissions. The letter's content included "the extent of time, the potential impact, and the outcomes of the research" (Creswell, 2017). During the conduct of the study, the researcher saw to it that she respected the research site by interrupting as little time as possible the routine of the participants. The study participants were provided with the needed information, thus participating in the potential research output. Such involvement in the study was essential because the results may form part of the basis for crafting initiatives and interventions to enhance the quality of the work life of educators.

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